

Developing Strategies on Elderly's Wellness Tourism in Phra Nakhon Si Ayutthaya Thailand.

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ABSTRACT: This paper aimed to study developing strategies on elderly's wellness tourism in phra nakhon si ayutthaya thailand. The sample 400 senior citizens in phra nakhon si ayutthaya thailand. They were obtained by convenience sampling and did not rely on possibility. A set of questionnaires was used for data collection and analyzed by using descriptive statistics. Also, there was an analysis of relationships of guidelines for developing marketing strategies having an effect on elderly's wellness tourism in phra nakhon si ayutthaya thailand. An analysis of correlation coefficient value and multi-stage multiple regression analysis were employed. Results of the study revealed that marketing strategies on product (X_1) ($\beta = 0.526$, $\alpha < .01$) and marketing strategies on personnel (X_5) ($\beta = 0.479$, $\alpha < .05$) had an effect on the success of elderly's wellness tourism in phra nakhon si ayutthaya thailand.

KEYWORDS- developing; elderly's ; wellness tourism.

I. INTRODUCTION

As the number of elderly people in Thailand has steadily increased in 2016, Is 13.2 percent of the total population Which according to the definition of the United Nations (UN) Defined as Any country with a population over the age of 60 accounts for more than 10 percent of the entire population. The country assumes that the country has entered an Aged Society when the proportion of the population Therefore, it can be considered that Thailand has stepped into Aging society then Longevity of the population is an indicator that the population is in good health. With a good quality of life, most activities include recreational activities. Tourism and Tourism Hobby etc.[1]

In 2014-2016, Thailand's health tourism saw an average annual growth rate of 7%, with an average annual income of approximately US \$ 9.2 million. And expected that in 2018 there will be tourists For health from international countries, one million visitors come to Thailand [2] Other factors that positively affect tourism Thai health also has reasonable medical expenses for the services that customers receive. Thai hospitality with hospitable Thai cuisine comprising a variety of healthy herbs. Thai traditional medicine and Thai massage. Moreover, the increase of non-communicable diseases such as diabetes, hypertension, obesity, head disease in the past 20 years has made the general public more inclined to care for health year Health promotion activities such as spas, food and wellness products become an integral part of the lifestyle of The lifestyles of people around the world therefore provide an opportunity for tourism-related businesses such as hotels and accommodation to Develop activities and products to promote health for tourists who are staying at[3]

Tourism has developed many forms. Make it attract the attention of Tourists include ecotourism. Adventure travel Geotourism Agricultural Tourism Science Historical tourism Cultural tourism Take a tour of rural life Blended tourism There is also another form of tourism. Which is becoming very popular with tourists right now, that is, health tourism (Health Tourism). On April 22, 2003, the Cabinet assigned the Ministry of Public Health. Establish a strategy to support Thailand as the Health Hub of Asia (Health Hub of Asia). or Medical Hub of Asia) according to the policy of economic and social restructuring. To add a tick National competitiveness Within a period of 5 years from the year 2004 until the year 2000 – 2008 Which has been targeting the product group (Product Line) in 3 groups, namely the service group Medical Service, Alternative

Health Service, and Thai health products and herbs (Herbal Product) with a goal that in a period of 5 years there will be Revenue from production totaled 210,815 million baht and focus on target groups of foreigners, including countries. In Asia, the Middle East and Europe[4]

Popular countries for The health care providers from the United States are India, Malaysia, Thailand and Turkey, respectively. Thailand is the most popular for health travelers. For those traveling for the health of Emirates Republic [5] From the performance index to Bloomberg Health Care Efficient Index (BHCEI) ranked A country with a population of 5 million or more and an average population of more than 70 years and a GDP of more than \$ 5,000 per year. Thailand ranked 27th (Up from No. 41 in 2017) of BHCEI from 56 countries worldwide, making it the ninth in Asia after Hong Kong, Singapore, South Korea, Japan, Australia, Taiwan, New Zealand and the People's Republic of China. China It is also worth noting that Thailand ranks BHCEI better than many developed countries, for example, Netherlands in 28th, UK number 35, Denmark number 41, Germany. No. 45 and USA No. 54 [6]

Strategy to develop Thailand as an international health center (2016-2025) The Upper North is a region that has the potential for tourism, both culturally Various tourist attractions It is the center of economy, transport, education, as well as the hospitableness of the people in the area. More groups of tourists are interested in Wellness Tourism and Long Stay. It is a big market that is interesting. And a market with great potential Especially foreigners who retire more than 30,000 people foreign groups, including Japanese as the main target group. And westerners are interested in coming to stay for a long time in the North. Which plays an important role in stimulating the tourism economy of the northern region It is a travel channel that Thailand has to prepare for the hospitality. Because it is a quality market And has a higher purchasing power in tourism than the general market Which must select tourism products to meet the needs of consumers And adding more facilities to accommodate the expansion of tourism. [7]

Phra Nakhon Si Ayutthaya Province is the longest past 417 years in the past. It is an important historical figure that is unique in both physical and physical aspects. History and civilization, the remains of the archaeological site are Currently, the Ayutthaya tourism situation continues to grow with the drama, causing more and more Thais to come to travel. That 2018 will grow 8 -10 percent so that the province's tourism growth rate is maintained is something to be aware of. [8]

As a result, more groups of tourists are interested in Wellness Tourism and Long Stay. It is interested in doing research on developing strategies on elderly's wellness tourism in phra nakhon si ayutthaya thailand To be a guideline for the development of cooperation in the tourism industry for elderly's wellness tourism in phra nakhon si ayutthaya thailand and to build confidence in foreign tourists. This could enable economic recovery in the service industry to return to normal and rapid growth.

II. OBJECTIVES/RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The objectives of this research article were to study developing strategies on developing on elderly's wellness tourism in phra nakhon si ayutthaya thailand

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The framework of this quantitative research is based on related concepts and theories to study marketing strategies that affect the developing on elderly's wellness tourism in phra nakhon si ayutthaya thailand with details as follows.

Figure 1 Conceptual framework of this study

Research Methodology

Population and sample group

The population was elderly's in phra nakhon si ayutthaya thailand The sample group consisted of 400 senior citizens in phra nakhon si ayutthaya thailand respondents by non-probability sampling and accidental sampling. The number was obtained by calculating the formula without the population at a 95% confidence level, and the sample size was set as follows

$$n = \frac{Z^2 P(1-P)}{E^2}$$

Where:

n = Size of the sample group

Z = Reliability level

P = Proportion of the population

E = Highest error value which will happen

The acceptance level was in accordance with the statistical significance level at 0.5

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 (0.5)(1-0.5)}{(0.05)^2}$$
$$= 384.16$$

The sample size was 385 respondents. However, 400 questionnaires were gathered by using a probabilistic sampling method between June - October 2020.

Research Instrument

The research tool was a questionnaire where the samples were asked individually to provide information about marketing developing on elderly's wellness tourism in phra nakhon si ayutthaya thailand. The content consisted of 4 parts as follows.

Part 1 : General data of personal information of elderly's wellness tourism in phra nakhon si ayutthaya thailand.

Part 2 : Data related to guidelines for developing elderly's wellness tourism in phra nakhon si ayutthaya thailand.

Part 3 : Data related to relationships of the guidelines.

Part 4 : Problems encountered and suggestions about the guidelines.

Data analyses

The data were collected by distributing questionnaires in the form of filling in information online to provide convenience and speed to comply with the situation of the COVID-19 outbreak.

The quantitative data were analyzed with descriptive statistics for the concordance between the developing on elderly's wellness tourism in phra nakhon si ayutthaya thailand and the set of results by analyzing the correlation coefficient and stepwise multiple regression.

IV. RESULTS

Table 1 Results develop elderly's wellness tourism in phra nakhon si ayutthaya thailand.

Marketing	Model 1			Model 2		
	B	SE B	β	B	SE	β
x_1 : product	0.438	0.052	0.446**	0.518	0.057	0.526**
x_5 personnel				0.442	0.076	0.479*
R^2		0.515			0.473	
R^2 Change					0.054	
F for change in R^2					4.354*	

Dependent Variable : develop elderly's wellness tourism in phra nakhon si ayutthaya thailand.

(Y) * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

According to Table 1, it was found that the develop elderly's wellness tourism in phra nakhon si ayutthaya thailand. on product (X_1) ($\beta = 0.526$, $\alpha < .01$) and personnel (X_5) ($\beta = 0.479$, $\alpha < .05$) had an effect on the elevation of international standards leading to wellness industry with a statistical significance level. This could be explained that variance of guidelines for develop wellness hotel in Northern Thailand to elevate international standards leading to wellness industry for ($R^2 = 0.515$). The predicting equation of the guidelines as a holistic dimension (Y) in the form of standard score was $Z_y = 0.526Z_{x_2} + 0.479Z_{x_3}$

V. DISCUSSIONS

The results revealed that overall marketing develop elderly's wellness tourism in phra nakhon si ayutthaya Thailand on product (X_1) ($\beta = 0.526$, $\alpha < .01$) and personnel (X_5) ($\beta = 0.479$, $\alpha < .05$) had an effect on the elevation of international standards leading to elderly's wellness tourism in phra nakhon si ayutthaya Thailand with a statistical significance level. This could be explained that variance of guidelines for develop elderly's wellness tourism in phra nakhon si ayutthaya Thailand to elevate international standards leading to wellness industry for ($R^2 = 0.515$). The predicting equation of the guidelines as a holistic dimension (Y) in the form of standard score was $Z_y = 0.526Z_{x_2} + 0.479Z_{x_3}$ This conformed to a study of Manerot [9] which found that marketing factors comprised the following : the expenses for medical treatment in Thailand is lower than other countries; promotion of Thai medical tourism abroad; and good quality of Thai medicine (Brand image). For organizational factors and managerial administration, the Thai government has a clear policy on the promotion of medical tourism. Meanwhile, personnel factors comprise professional management because it is

mostly private hospitals having readiness on specialist doctors and friendly service. This also conformed to a study of Theeranon [10] which found that Thailand has competitive advantage in terms of readiness in medical service and tourism with high standard of services. Besides, it was found that hospitals in Thailand are certified most in Asia on the basis of international standards (Join Commission International : JCI). It also conformed to the World Economic Forum [11] which revealed that Thailand had advantage in health service since the country is well accepted by foreign tourists in terms of health service resulting in the continual expansion of wellness tourism.

VI. CONCLUSION

Tourism is one of the important factors in a quality lifestyle. Traveler Not limited to young people only. If including the population of all ages, even The elderly can also travel for tourism, leisure and health tourism. Of the elderly who tended to travel more according to statistics of the increasing of the elderly population As a result The government should develop the tourism industry in line with the needs of the elderly. Promote the organization of tourism programs suitable for the elderly. Add tourist service points, develop sources Travel in good condition To reach the elderly who want to Tourist attractions that are provinces that operate for leisure tourism and health tourism.

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